

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF QUALITATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF A PERSON IN ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the field of phraseology, a section of lexicology, in which the qualitative component phraseologisms mainly in English and Uzbek linguistics are analyzed comparatively, valuable information is given about phraseological units, which reflect the mentality, culture, customs and traditions of a particular nation. This article is devoted to a comparative study of the national-cultural specifics of phraseological units with a component of a body part in English, Russian and Uzbek languages. The research is conditioned by the importance of comparative study of languages in order to identify their national and cultural specifics. The choice of proverbs for research is explained not only by their widespread use in everyday life, but also by the fact that they are expressive, figurative, vividly reflect the peculiarities of the spiritual and material life of the people.

Keywords: national and cultural specificity, comparative study of languages, peculiarities of the spiritual life of the people, cultural information, comparative characteristics.

Linguoculturology is a generalization science that occurs between the sciences of culturology and Linguistics, deals with the study of phenomena such as the interaction and interconnectedness of language and culture, the formation of this link, as well as its reflection outside the language and language as a holistic system. Linguoculturology, on the one hand, studies the role of mankind in cultural linguistics, and on the other hand, yesa, the position of man in linguistics. Each language is very closely connected with the history of the owners of the language and also manifests some special aspects of their traditional everyday life, geography, culture that are not written about. In our fast-paced time, people more and more often go out into the world, there are intercultural contacts.

People have become more proficient in other languages for communication, so it becomes necessary for them to know the cultural component of the language. In this regard, recently, studies of the language in terms of its interaction with culture have become extremely relevant, in connection with which a new special

direction has appeared, called cultural linguistics. Cultural linguistics, the development of which began in the early 90s, is today one of the most relevant areas of modern linguistics, whose tasks include the study and description of the relationship and mutual influences of language and culture, language and folk mentality. It has to do with both cultural science and language science. Cultural linguistics studies the national and cultural semantics of linguistic units in order to understand them in their entirety of content and shades, to the extent that is as close as possible to their perception by the speakers of a given language and a given culture. In a word, this is an aspect of linguistics that studies the problem of reflecting national culture in a language. The most complete relationship "language - culture" is reflected in the works of W. von Humboldt, who wrote: "Man predominantly: he lives with objects as the language presents them to him. Each language describes the circle of the people to whom it belongs, the circle from which a person is given to leave only insofar as it enters the circle of another language. "One of the linguistic units, an important component of which is cultural information, is a phraseological unit. About phraseological units are written very -very much, they are grammatic, semantic and syntactic analyzed, but not sufficiently studied linguomadanically.

German scientist V for the first time in the relations of language and culture. Gumbolt expresses in his works the following: "the more the language of Man gives him information about the subject, the more he lives in this way. Any language will express the way of its existence of the people to which the person belongs" M.M. Pokrovsky, G.V. Stepanov, A. A. Potebnya, D.S. Likhachev and Y.M. Lotman, F.i. Busayev gave scientific justification to linguoculturology as a science, as a result of his research.

The first research in Uzbek linguistics devoted to linguistics SH. Safarov, D. Khudoyberganov, N. Mahmudov and Sh. Carried out by the usmanovas. In recent years, great importance has been attached to studying Uzbek phraseology from a linguistic, cognitive scientific point of view, comparing it with other languages. Including B. Safaraliyev, G. Boqiyeva, N. Nasrullayeva studied phrases semantically in religious, mythical, historical, literature-related, geographical and national conceptual spheres. Professor A. Mamatov will dwell on the fact that the phrases are formed in historically-etymologically in different ways. According to the scientist, the phraseological units differ, firstly, from the phraseologisms formed on the basis of the Uzbek phenomenon, and secondly, from the fraternal and non-traditional languages,

which came into being by mastering and kalkalash. In the book “explanatory phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek language”, Shavkat Rakhmatullaev mentions that the main part of the phrases in Uzbek linguistics consists of phraseological units Fe'l, as well as ot-component, qualitative and adverbial phrases.

Chinese researcher YU Wang categorizes English phrases into eight categories in terms of syntax.

1) Sentence idioms. -Gap iboralar. Butter wouldn't melt in your mouth. Your chickens come home to roost.

2) Semi-sentence idioms. -Yarim gap iboralar. Take the bad with the good, keep a bad eye on smb/sth.

3) Verbal phrases. -Fe'lli birikmalar. Beat up, come across.

4) Prepositional phrases. -Predlogli brikmalar. By the dozen, in doubt.

5) Nominal idioms. -Nominal iboralar. Good faith, a golden handshake.

6) Adjective idioms. -Sifatli iboralar. Far and away, full of beans.

As a consequence, we can come to the conclusion that phraseological units are a very valuable source of knowledge about the culture of the people and are a direct etymological reflection of the national and cultural specifics of a particular linguistic community, and that is why at this time phraseological units are the brightest linguistic unit of expression linguistic culture. Phraseological units can be studied in cultural linguistics from positions without equivalence, reflection in their structure of mythologemes, historical facts, traditions and customs, imagery, value norms and behavior, etc. Thus, PU (phraseological units) is the most studied culturally-marked unit of the language, since PU reflect the national-cultural specifics of the language, its originality. The phraseological unit captures the rich historical experience of the people, it reflects ideas related to work, life and culture of people. The study of phraseology is a necessary link in the assimilation of the language, in improving the culture of speech. The correct and appropriate use of phraseological units gives speech a unique originality, special expressiveness, accuracy, imagery. That is why, the task of our research includes the analysis of phraseological units from the point of view of their national and cultural specifics. As the analysis of our material has shown, phraseological units with a component of a body part are also of particular interest for linguoculturological studies. This group of phraseological units is a clear example of the action of not only linguistic, but also extralinguistic factors in the language. It is during their analysis that it is possible to identify both common features inherent in the human community,

regardless of linguistic affiliation, and specific features due to purely extralinguistic factors. The main element of any comparison is the identification of identical (integral) and distinctive (differential) features of the compared phenomena. The postulate of identities and differences in language, formed by F. de Saussure, underlies a number of the most important methods of language analysis - opposing, field, transformational, component, etc. "As a result of formal and semantic comparison and opposition, members of language systems of any scale - grammatical paradigms, antonymic pairs, etc., and vice versa, an exhaustive description of any individual linguistic phenomenon presupposes the allocation of a set of various aspects, forms, meanings and other differences in it, and on the other hand, the inclusion of this phenomenon in various communities on the basis of some identities - formal, semantic, functional, etc. " [Saussure, 2000]. Comparison of specific phraseological units provided researchers with material for generalizations in various directions: in translation theory, in phraseography theory, in comparative typological studies.

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